

Nanoscale Phase Segregation on Binary-Coated Nanoparticles Analyzed by MALDI-MS: Influence of Patchy Morphology

Javier Reguera^{*,†,‡,§}

[†]CIC biomaGUNE, Paseo de Miramón 182, 20014 Donostia/San Sebastián, Spain

[‡]Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48013 Bilbao, Spain

[§]Biomedical Research Networking Center in Bioengineering Biomaterials and Nanomedicine, Ciber-BBN, 20014 Donostia/San Sebastián, Spain

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Nanoscale phase segregation of several ligands on nanoparticle surfaces is a key feature that strongly impacts on the nanoparticle properties and hence on their final applications. Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry (MALDI-MS) has appeared as a powerful technique to characterize the surface phase segregation of binary mixtures of ligands in nanoparticle self-assembled monolayers. By comparing the mass spectra of clusters of ligands desorbed by MALDI with calculated random distribution, nanoparticles can be classified by their degree of nanophasic segregation. Here, the influence of the selected cluster size and ligand ratio on the classification segregation parameters has been theoretically explored. Two different segregation procedures have been evaluated yielding two different morphologies, elongated and random patches. Results show that segregation parameters are influenced, apart from general segregation, by the morphology of patches. This influence is different depending on the size of the selected clusters of ligands enabling the use of segregation parameter ratios to obtain morphological information. The simultaneous analysis of different cluster sizes can then be used to expand the applicability of this powerful technique providing more complete information of the nanoscale phase segregation and, therefore, enabling a better understanding of the nanostructure–properties relationship.

■ INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticle science has evolved remarkably in the last few years and has become one of the main enablers in many technologies such as biomedicine, optics, electronics, catalysis, sensing, etc. One of the key features of nanoparticles is their high surface-to-volume ratio that allows an easy incorporation of a large number of functional molecules at their surface per total amount of used material. Moreover, the combination of several ligands highly increases their multifunctionality and versatility.¹ Depending on the nature of these ligands and the nanoparticle synthesis method, these molecules can arrange in different nanostructures at the surface. Binary ligands, for instance, can go from random distributions to Janus morphologies, passing through intermediate phase segregation in smaller nanodomains, or patches. The surface properties of nanoparticles depend on the chemical nature of ligands, but also, they are greatly influenced by their surface arrangement. One typical example is the adsorption of Janus amphiphilic nanoparticles at interfaces that is several times stronger than for the equivalent homogeneous nanoparticles.^{2,3} Other examples are the structure-dependent nanoparticle solubility,⁴ the change of functionality by buried ligands,⁵ or the increase in cell membrane penetration and cell uptake for surface structured nanoparticles.^{6,7}

Given the importance of phase segregation on nanoparticle surfaces, several techniques have been applied to characterize

their structure.^{8–11} Among them, there are atomistic and coarse grain simulations,^{12–18} atomic force microscopy,¹⁹ scanning tunneling microscopy,^{20–23} IR,^{24,25} small-angle neutron scattering,^{26,27} electron spin resonance,²⁸ NMR,^{29–32} or electron microscopy.^{33–35} All of them have some limitations, either in the number of analyzable nanoparticles, in the type of ligands or chemical groups, or in the difficulty and time required to achieve a clear conclusion. In fact, the combination of more than one complementary technique would probably be required nowadays to prove unequivocally a kind of ligand structure.

One powerful technique that has appeared in the last few years to classify phase segregation of nanoparticle ligand coating is matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI) with different modalities (MALDI-IM-MS, MALDI-TOF, LDI-MS, etc.). The use of this technique for ligand segregation analysis was described initially by Harkness et al. for gold nanoparticles coated by binary mixtures of ligands,³⁶ and since then several works have applied it to other types of ligands and silver nanoparticles.^{37–40} This technique assumes that metal–thiolate complexes are desorbed as discrete portions of the monolayer. Therefore, nanophasic

segregation in the monolayer will be reflected in the relative abundances of homoleptic and heteroleptic metal–thiolate complex ions, from which the degree of nanoparticle segregation in the monolayer of the metal nanoparticle can be calculated.

Basically, a cluster size, in terms of a defined number of ligands, is selected from all the desorbed clusters from the nanoparticle. This cluster will have a mass spectrum with different masses (m/z) depending on the ligand composition. By comparing the relative intensities of the obtained mass spectrum to the ones theoretically expected for a completely random arrangement of ligands, it is possible to identify phase segregation, i.e., the more phase segregation there is in the nanoparticle, the higher the difference will be with the theoretical random distribution. In the literature, this difference has been calculated through the residual sum of squares (also called sum-squares residuals, SSR). To calculate the SSR, first, a cluster with a certain number of ligands and metal atoms is selected, $M_m - L_n$, where n is the number of ligands and m is the number of metal atoms. When mixtures of two ligands with two different masses are used, the cluster produces $n + 1$ peaks in the mass spectrum reflecting the different possible combinations of ligands. The ligand ratio $p \in (0, 1)$ can be calculated from this spectrum as follows

$$\theta_i = \frac{C_i}{\sum_{i=0}^n C_i}, \quad p = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{i \theta_i}{n} \quad (1)$$

where i is the peak number from lower to higher mass (from 0 to n), C_i is the peak intensity in the mass spectrum, and θ_i is the normalized intensity (note here that this ligand ratio is the one measured in the spectrum and does not need to be exactly the one on the nanoparticle, due to small differences in ionization/desorption, in fact, small differences in p_n could be obtained through different cluster sizes of the same spectrum). Given a ligand ratio, the relative intensities corresponding to a random distribution, $\theta_{i,\text{binomial}}$, could be calculated with the binomial function as

$$\theta_{i,\text{binomial}} = \binom{n}{i} p^i (1-p)^{(n-i)} \quad (2)$$

The SSR is then calculated from the two different normalized intensities.

$$\text{SSR} = \sum_{i=0}^n (\theta_i - \theta_{i,\text{binomial}})^2 \quad (3)$$

As mentioned, SSR has been the chosen parameter used to classify nanoparticles as a function of their phase segregation in all previous works. Although SSR could be calculated for different sizes of clusters (SSR_n , with n the number of ligands) of the same spectrum, previous works in the literature have performed this calculation based only on one cluster size (typically Au_4L_4 , and Ag_6L_5 for gold and silver nanoparticles, respectively). This selection is generally based on the higher abundance of those cluster species, but although not mentioned, it could be also due to the different ranges of SSR values obtained for the same nanoparticle depending on the selected cluster size.

In this work, the parameter SSR is analyzed and its limitations are explained. A new segregation parameter S is proposed to better classify the segregation of ligands. Then, this new segregation parameter is analyzed depending on the chosen cluster size ($n = 2, 3, \dots$), the ligand ratio, and the

segregation degree. Finally, the segregation parameters are tested with two theoretical segregation experiments that tend to form different patch morphologies, to understand the influence of the cluster size selected.

■ EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Nanoparticle Design. The theoretical nanoparticle was created in an array of $l \times l$ ligands disposed in a close-packed hexagonal arrangement. The array was created boundaryless (periodic boundary conditions) to better mimic the boundaryless spherical surface (i.e., in the theoretical nanoparticle the ligand at the position $(l + 1, l + 1)$ corresponds to the ligand at position $(1, 1)$). The size of the nanoparticle was selected to be 48×48 ligands. Assuming a ligand surface of 0.216 nm^2 ,⁴¹ this would correspond to a nanoparticle size of $\sim 12.6 \text{ nm}$ in diameter, very close to the typical sizes obtained in the Turkevich synthesis method of metallic nanoparticles ($d \sim 13 \text{ nm}$), probably one of the most used synthesis for metallic nanoparticles.⁴² Results for 19×19 ligands ($\sim 5 \text{ nm}$ nanoparticle) are given in the Supporting Information (SI).

Cluster Composition Calculations. Given a size of cluster to analyze, the relative count of the different ligand compositions was calculated as follows. For every ligand position (i, j) , the cluster formed by this ligand and its neighbors was examined. As different neighbors could be selected to form these clusters, only the ones that would not be repeated when another ligand is analyzed are counted. For example, for $n = 2$, only the clusters formed by $\{(i, j), (i + 1, j)\}$, $\{(i, j), (i, j + 1)\}$, and $\{(i, j), (i - 1, j)\}$ are considered. For clusters bigger than 2, only the cluster formed by compact structures were selected, i.e., the ones that maximize ligand contacts (see Figure S1). The selected cluster sizes were chosen from $n = 2$ to 7 ligands.

Segregation through Ligand Exchange. The iterative procedure was carried out by a random selection of two ligands. They were interchanged when a more favorable situation was obtained, i.e., in the case where the number of adjacent neighbors of the same species was higher. The routine was repeated, and the segregation parameters SSR_n and S_n were regularly calculated at a selected number of ligand exchange steps. The procedure was stopped when no further change in the segregation parameter was achieved.

Note here that as the procedure only counts the interaction of the adjacent neighbors, interactions at longer range are not considered being unable to achieve a complete phase segregation in Janus for nanoparticles above a certain size.

This procedure was repeated several times (at least 15 and 30 times for 12.6 and 5 nm nanoparticles, respectively) starting from different random distributions. The results were averaged to obtain a more realistic information of the cluster morphology. The error bar of these measurements was calculated as the standard deviation.

Segregation through Lateral Displacement. In this routine, one ligand is selected randomly. This ligand is allowed to interchange with the first or second neighbor in only one direction when it reaches a more favorable situation depending on the adjacent neighbors (number of ligands of the same species among the six surrounding neighbors). The routine was repeated, and the segregation parameters were calculated regularly at a selected number of steps. The procedure was stopped when no further changes in the segregation parameter was achieved.

Figure 1. (A) Representation of a model nanoparticle surface formed by 48×48 ligands, the ligands are arranged in a hexagonal array with a boundaryless nanoparticle surface. The Janus morphology is designed by selecting a $l \times l$ patch of a certain ligand (pink ligands) and the rest being occupied by the other ligand (blue). The patch size is indicated below every representation together with the ligand ratio. (B) Dependence of SSR_n with the ligand ratio of the Janus nanoparticle represented in (A) at several cluster sizes. (C) Same dependence, but with the use of the S_n parameter. Note that the y-axis is in the log scale and different from graph (B).

This procedure was repeated several times (at least 15 and 30 times for 12.6 and 5 nm nanoparticles respectively) starting from different random distributions. The results were averaged to obtain a more realistic information of the cluster morphology. The error bars of these measurements were calculated as the standard deviation.

RESULTS

To better understand the SSR value, it is first necessary to know its variation range. The lower limit is obviously 0 that would be given by no differences in the two compared normalized intensities $\theta_{i,\text{binomial}} = \theta_i$. On the other hand, the maximum can be obtained by comparing the binomial distribution $\theta_{i,\text{binomial}}$ with a distribution in which only two mass peaks corresponding to the homoleptic species are present, i.e., in an ideal Janus configuration (Figure S2A in the Supporting Information, SI). The SSR_{Max} for a given cluster size (n ligands) could be calculated as

$$SSR_{\text{Max},n} = ((1-p)\theta_{0,\text{binomial}})^2 + (p - \theta_{n,\text{binomial}})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\theta_{i,\text{binomial}})^2 \quad (4)$$

There is therefore, a clear dependence of the maximum $SSR_{\text{Max},n}$ with the ligand ratio p . The variation of this ligand is especially important at ligand ratios far from the equimolar ligand ratio $p = 0.5$ (Figure S2 in the SI shows this variation). In addition, there is also a dependency of $SSR_{\text{Max},n}$ with the cluster size selected, limiting the nanoparticle classification with this parameter. To exemplify this variation dependency, we have performed the calculation of SSR on a theoretical boundaryless model nanoparticle of 48×48 ligands in which the two types of ligands are segregated in a Janus structure,

forming one of the ligands a $l \times l$ patch (Figure 1A). Even if all the nanoparticles correspond to Janus morphology, the obtained SSR (Figure 1B) highly varies with the ligand ratio, decreasing more than 1 order of magnitude for ligand ratios below 0.1. This variation is more prominent when the smallest cluster size is selected ($n = 2$). A straightforward solution to avoid this variation with the ligand ratio could be provided by normalizing SSR with the maximum value that can be achieved at each p . The new normalized segregation parameter S_n will vary between 0 and 1 and it can be calculated from eqs 3 and 4 as follows

$$S_n = \frac{SSR_n}{SSR_{\text{Max},n}} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n (\theta_i - \theta_{i,\text{binomial}})^2}{((1-p)\theta_{0,\text{binomial}})^2 + (p - \theta_{n,\text{binomial}})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\theta_{i,\text{binomial}})^2} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1C shows the benefits of using S_n values instead of SSR. There are minimal variations of S for all ligand ratios of the Janus nanoparticle, and only a very small decrease is produced for the smallest ligand ratio, $p = 0.016$. The obtained S_n value slightly below 1 is produced by the line interface between the two patches of the Janus nanoparticle, and it is only relevant under very low ligand ratios or very small nanoparticle sizes. Using this new parameter, reported experimental results could be reexamined and dramatic changes in the classification of nanostructure segregation are expected for ligand ratios close to 0 or 1 (Figure S3 in the SI shows an example). Notice also that S_n slightly varies with the selected cluster size (with n), i.e., with the probe size used to analyze the nanoparticle. This is due to the different sensitivities of this probe size to the line interface between the two ligand domains and, therefore, it

Figure 2. (A) Snapshots of the nanoparticle surface representing several segregation regions in a ligand exchange segregation procedure (in this case $p = 0.5$). (B–E) Plots of the average segregation ratios S_3/S_2 (B), S_4/S_2 (C), S_5/S_2 (D), S_6/S_2 (E), and S_7/S_2 (F) as a function of S_2 and at different ligand ratios. Error bars represent the standard deviation after averaging several segregation experiments. Segregation ratios for other cluster sizes can be seen in [Figure S5](#).

should be affected not only by the size of the patches but probably also by the shape of those patches.

This last observation led us to examine the combined analysis of different cluster sizes to obtain information not only about the final segregation but also about the patchy morphology. In fact, a simple experiment could be generated by the formation of a Janus nanoparticle with constant number of ligands but varying from one ligand thickness to a more rounded shape (SI, [Figure S3](#)). By analyzing the change of S_n with shape, it can be demonstrated that the more elongated shapes tend to have lower values of S_n . This is expected, as there is an increase in line interface between the two patches. More interestingly, the difference between the different S_n parameters tends to be larger when very narrow nanodomains are reached (one or two ligand thicknesses). It should be pointed out here, that the use of only one segregation parameter, even if this is calculated for all the cluster sizes at the same time,

cannot give information about the patchy morphology as different morphologies could give rise to the same segregation parameter. Therefore, the use of more than one segregation parameter is a requirement to obtain morphological information, and not only a classification of nanoparticles by their ligand segregation.

To better understand the relation among the different segregation parameters S_n with the shape of the patches, the ligand ratio, and the size of the patches, we have performed more irregular and “realistic” patch formation. A nanoparticle with randomly generated ligand distribution was initially created. The ligands were then allowed to move to increase their segregation using two different procedures: segregation through a ligand exchange process that formed random patches and a segregation through a lateral displacement performed only in one direction. More rounded patches were formed in the first case, while more elongated ones, oriented in one

Figure 3. A) Snapshots of the nanoparticle representing two segregation states for a lateral displacement segregation procedure ($p = 0.4$). (B–E) Plots of the average segregation ratios S_3/S_2 (B), S_4/S_2 (C), S_5/S_2 (D), S_6/S_2 (E), and S_7/S_2 (F) as a function of S_2 and at different ligand ratios. Error bars represent the standard deviation after averaging several segregation experiments. Segregation ratios for other cluster sizes can be seen in Figure S6.

direction, and with a narrow form (typically 1–3 ligand thickness for the minority ligand) were obtained in the second case.

Figure 2A shows snapshots of the segregation procedure through ligand exchange. Although a strict classification is difficult, and the visual appearance can change depending on the ligand ratio and nanoparticle size, we can talk about the region of large segregation (including Janus) for $S \in (0.1, 1)$, segregation in small patches $S \in (0.01, 0.1)$, and a region of very low segregation $S < 0.01$ where it is visually almost indistinguishable from a random distribution. To understand the ratios between different segregation parameters (S_m/S_n with $m > n$), we performed several ligand exchange experiments for each ligand ratio, each one starting from a different generated random distribution. The experiments were then represented as a function of segregation S_2 , and the segregation ratios S_m/S_n were averaged at each S_2 . Figure 2B–E

shows these segregation ratios by comparing the segregations at different cluster sizes with S_2 (S_m/S_2 vs S_2 with p varying from 0.05 to 0.5). At first sight, it is easy to observe the high influence of the ligand ratio p on the segregation ratios. This variation with p tends to be higher when the cluster size is more different. For S_7/S_2 , for instance, it varies from values below 1 at equimolar concentrations ($p = 0.5$) to more than 6 for ligand ratios of $p < 0.05$. Similar dependency with the ligand ratio, although less pronounced, is observed for other segregation ratios (SI, Figure S5). In addition to the ligand ratio dependence, ratios also vary with the segregation degree S_2 . This variation tends to be small at low segregation degrees (in the region of random and small domain segregation), whereas at high segregation degrees (large patches) there is a higher variation and the ratios converge to a value close to 1.

A similar experiment with a lateral displacement segregation was also carried out. Figure 3A shows a snapshot of two

Figure 4. Ratios of segregation parameters S_x/S_2 (with x from 3 to 7, (A–E)) for the different patch morphologies. Elongated patches are represented in blue, while the more rounded patches produced by ligand exchange are represented in red. The plots are expressed as a function of the ligand ratio p and fixing the segregation $S_2 = 0.02$ in the small domains region. For $p \in (0.5, 1)$ the results are omitted since the graph is symmetric with respect to $p = 0.5$.

different states, an initial random distribution and a final segregation in small elongated nanodomains. Using this procedure, no further segregation is possible as they would lose the elongated shape. In any case, similar to the previous experiment, there is an increase in the segregation ratios S_m/S_2 (Figure 3B–E) as we go further from the equimolar ligand ratio (decrease p). In this case, for the range of segregation tested (up to small domain formation), the ratios remain relatively constant. Also, similar to the last procedure, a variation in the ligand ratio, although less pronounced, was observed for the other segregation ratios (SI, Figure S6).

The comparison between the two kinds of arrangements can be done at selected S_2 segregation regions. Figure 4 shows this comparison of S_x/S_2 ratios in the small domain region (at $S_2 = 0.02$). As mentioned above, there is a high variation from values below 1 to values much higher than 1 when the ligand ratio changes from $p = 0.5$ to lower values. More interestingly, there is a clear difference between the two types of patches. This variation depends on the selected couple of cluster sizes. In general, the elongated patches show lower values than the random patches for ligand ratios close to 0.5 and higher values for low ligand ratios. The point of the ligand ratio where the tendency is inverted depends on the selected cluster sizes. For instance, in the S_m/S_2 series, (Figure 4) for the small cluster difference S_3/S_2 , the elongated patches show higher values for

almost all ligand ratios. As the difference between cluster sizes increases the inversion point moves to lower values (for S_7/S_2 $p_{\text{inv}} \sim 0.3$). For the rest of cluster ratios (Figure 5) clear differences between the two types of patches are also observed. The effect of the patch shape however is highly dependent on the pair of segregation parameters selected and the ligand ratio region. Most of these ratios show similar inversion behavior than S_x/S_2 (S_4/S_3 and S_5/S_3 for instance), on the other hand, there are ratios with no inversion (S_6/S_4) or with different trends (S_7/S_6 or S_6/S_5 for instance).

This behavior is also observed in other selected S_2 values in the small patch region (Figures S7 and S8). On the other hand, for much lower S_2 values, in the region of very low segregation, there are also some differences although much less significant and with bigger errors (Figures S9 and S10). This was expected as only some “embryonic” patches are formed at this region being the difference between the two morphologies of very little significance.

The calculations shown above were performed on ~ 13 nm nanoparticles. Decreasing the size of the nanoparticle produces almost identical results as shown in the SI for ~ 5 nm nanoparticles (Figures S11–S16). This is expected as the results reflect only the relationship between the ligand interfaces and ligand bulk and are not affected by the nanoparticle size. Note here that when nanoparticles are

Figure 5. Ratios of segregation parameters S_x/S_y (for different combination cluster sizes from 3 to 7, (A–J)) for the two different segregation procedures. Elongated patches are represented in blue, while the more rounded patches produced by ligand exchange are represented in red. The plots are expressed as a function of the ligand ratio p and fixing the segregation $S_2 = 0.02$ in the small domain region. For $p \in (0.5, 1)$ the results are omitted since the graph is symmetric with respect to $p = 0.5$.

synthesized with binary ligand coatings, the nanoparticle size affects the type of nanostructure,^{12,32,43} therefore, in a MALDI-MS experiment the polydispersity should be kept relatively low to have all nanoparticles with the same type of surface nanostructure and reliable results.

One clear difference, when the calculations of the two sizes are compared, is the higher error bars for the smaller nanoparticles. This is a consequence of how the values are averaged. In a MALDI-MS experiment the segregation values would be given by the spectrum obtained from the ligand clusters of a very large number of nanoparticles, thus, the ligand ratios will not have error bars (unless the experiment is repeated). On the other hand, in the theoretical calculation,

the segregation ratios are calculated for every nanoparticle and then averaged. When the nanoparticle size is decreased, the number of patches per nanoparticle decreases and the value varies more from the morphological representative one, therefore increasing the error. In addition, the variability in the ligand ratios can also contribute, to a lesser extent, to the error bars. The initial theoretical nanoparticles are created by disposing the ligands randomly with a certain probability equal to the ligand ratio. Then, the ligand ratio will vary from nanoparticle to nanoparticle following a normal distribution. The standard deviation will depend on the number of ligands in the nanoparticles as $\sigma = \sqrt{p(1-p)/n_{\text{lig}}}$ that corresponds

to a binomial distribution (p is the ligand ratio and n_{lig} is the number of ligands). Therefore, a decrease in the nanoparticle size will increase the variability of these ligand ratios. For instance, for $p = 0.5$, the standard deviation of ligand ratios changes from 0.1 to 0.26 when the nanoparticle size decreases from 12.6 to 5 nm. Experimentally, it is not known how the ligand ratios vary from nanoparticle to nanoparticle, but it should be at least a normal distribution equal to the calculations mentioned above making them more realistic.

■ CONCLUSIONS

We have evaluated the use of MALDI as a powerful technique to understand nanophase segregation of ligands on nanoparticle coatings. This technique allows the analysis of a wide set of binary mixtures and could be easily extrapolated to more than two ligands combinations. The sum-squares residual is the parameter that has been used to classify the nanoparticles according to their nanoscale segregation. We have observed that this parameter has limitations when nanoparticles of different ligand ratios are compared, and we propose a normalized sum-squares residual or segregation parameter (S_n) that varies between 0 and 1 and yields more comparable values among the different ligand ratios.

Different segregation parameters could be obtained in an experimental analysis by choosing different ligand cluster sizes, i.e., by changing the probe size used to analyze the nanoparticle. We have observed that these parameters change with the segregation, ligand ratio, and morphology of patches formed during segregation. By analyzing the clusters of 2–7 ligands, we have observed a clear dependence of the segregation ratios on the morphology of the formed patches. In general, the segregation ratios S_m/S_n (with $m > n$) tend to be higher for elongated patches when the ligand ratio is close to equimolar ratios, while they tend to be lower for small ligand ratios. The results expand the possibilities of this technique to better classify the segregation that takes place on the surface of nanoparticles coated by more than one ligand and contribute to improve our understanding of the nanoscale structure–properties relationship.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

📄 Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: [10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b06286](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b06286).

Selection of desorption clusters, a representation of SSR_{Max} , the influence of patch shape in a model Janus nanoparticle, the re-examination of published experimental data with the S parameter, the average segregation ratios vs S_2 and a comparison at fixed values, and the segregation ratio analysis for 5 nm nanoparticle (PDF)

Data of averaged segregation ratios for 12.6 and 5 nm nanoparticles (XLS)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: javier.reguera@uva.es

ORCID

Javier Reguera: [0000-0001-5110-5361](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5110-5361)

Notes

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